

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Abca9.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Abca9 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Piehler, A., Kaminski, W.E., Wenzel, J.J., Langmann, T. and Schmitz, G., 2002. Molecular
12 structure of a novel cholesterol-responsive A subclass ABC transporter, ABCA9. *Biochemical and
13 biophysical research communications*, 295(2), pp.408-416.